

Original Research Paper

Evaluating the implementation of a rapid access atrial fibrillation clinic utilising a pharmacist-physician model of care

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Atrial fibrillation
Stroke
Pharmacist
Health care quality
Access
And evaluation
Anti-arrhythmia agents

ABSTRACT

Background: Time to assessment and treatment of atrial fibrillation (AF) is critical for reducing stroke risk. However, Australian data have shown low uptake of timely anticoagulation, with people in regional areas having a greater risk of low uptake compared to people in metropolitan areas.

Objective: To conduct a retrospective, mixed methods evaluation of a pharmacist-physician model of care for a rapid access atrial fibrillation (RAAF) clinic in a large regional centre in Victoria, Australia.

Methods: The RAAF clinic involved telehealth pharmacist appointments and face-to-face physician consults and aimed to see patients within 14 days of referral. A retrospective mixed-methods evaluation was adopted. Quantitative methods included time-based analysis of appointment statistics, analyses of the proportion of patients meeting known quality indicators for risk assessment and treatment for AF. Qualitative analysis included conventional content analysis of patient feedback and net promoter scoring to understand patient acceptability.

Results: There were 312 patients referred to the service during 2022–2023, 274 (88 %) patients participated in 268 pharmacist and 421 physician appointments. Median days from referral to first clinic consultation were 14 (inter quartile range 9–20). Proportion of high-risk patients (CHADSVA >1) who received anticoagulation for stroke prevention increased from 88 % pre-clinic to 97 % post-clinic. Anti-arrhythmic therapies were used by 76 % of patient's pre-clinic and 73 % post-clinic, with changes to therapy occurring in 35 % of patients. Patients were highly accepting of the service, with a mean patient acceptability score of 9 out of 10. Qualitative analysis illustrated that positive patient experience was linked to clinician performance, as well as the organisational structure and workflow of the clinic itself.

Conclusions: A pharmacist-physician model of care was successfully implemented in a regional health setting, leading to improved access and medication management, with high levels of patient acceptance.

1. Introduction

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is increasingly a major cause of hospital admissions, with the global prevalence of AF increasing by 146 % from 1990 to 2019^{1–4}. In addition, people with AF are more likely to be hospitalised, with annual hospitalization rates of 10–40 %.⁵ This can be due to increased risk of heart failure, symptomatic AF, as well as complications associated with anticoagulant and anti-arrhythmic

therapies.^{5,6}

Paradigm shifts in the management of AF have occurred in recent years, with the last three international AF guidelines recommending earlier rhythm control and stroke prevention strategies, partnered with patient-centred multidisciplinary care.^{5,7,8} In 2019, the Victorian Agency for Health Information released a commissioned report, informed by a 2011 to 2013 cohort of hospitalised patients with a primary or secondary diagnosis of AF. This report showed that only 22–40

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2025.03.005>

Received 14 August 2024; Received in revised form 19 February 2025; Accepted 4 March 2025

Available online 6 March 2025

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% of patients were dispensed an oral anticoagulant on discharge from hospital.⁹ Indeed, over 95 % of the 33,806 patient cohort were noted to have a CHADS-VA risk greater than 1, where guidelines recommend anticoagulation to prevent stroke,⁷ indicating a substantial deviation from guideline-recommended care.

Timely access to care is particularly important in AF, given that longer periods without anticoagulation lead to a higher cumulative risk of stroke and therefore a higher likelihood of quality of life-limiting symptoms.¹⁰ In addition, even when cardiology appointments occur, there is frequently insufficient information required for healthcare professionals to make a comprehensive assessment, further extending treatment delays.¹¹

There is evidence that Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation (RAAF) clinics internationally and within Australia via a cardiologist led model can lead to reduced hospitalization and death via early investigation and treatment.^{6,12} However, many of the previous studies were conducted in major cities where there is greater access to cardiologists when compared to regional areas.¹³ It is imperative that new patient-centred, outcome based, models of care are implemented that can deliver integrated AF care in settings where access to cardiologists may be limited.^{14,15}

This study describes a retrospective, mixed methods evaluation of a pharmacist-physician model of care for a RAAF clinic established in a large regional centre in Victoria, Australia. This model of care was designed to accelerate a patient's access to risk assessment, anticoagulation and arrhythmia treatment, as well as enhance patient quality of life and service satisfaction.

2. Methods

2.1. Pharmacist-physician model of care

Due to limited access to cardiologists, mainly due to staff availability, a model of care was designed utilising existing skillsets via a pharmacist-physician model. This model involved patients receiving an initial consult with a specialist cardiology pharmacist via telehealth, followed by a face to face or telehealth consultation with a general medicine physician with experience working in stroke clinics (Fig. 1). The referral was triaged by the pharmacist, and a pharmacy technician contacted the patient and booked the telehealth pharmacist appointment and the physician appointment based on patient preference and clinic availability. Patients were provided a written information sheet on atrial

fibrillation and their relevant medications that was emailed or posted based on preference.

The telehealth pharmacist consultation was designed in line with the 'ABC' integrated care guidelines for AF, as well as recommendations from national and international AF guidelines.^{10,14,16} Pharmacists were given flexibility to adapt the consultation as needed to suit the patient's situation and needs, but there were key components each consultation needed to address. Firstly, patients were asked about their understanding of AF and the reasons behind their referral to the clinic. Education on AF and expectations around likely diagnostic and treatment pathways were explained by the pharmacist. Patients were then assessed for stroke and bleeding risk via CHADS-VA and HASBLED scoring.^{7,10} In addition, the pharmacist provided recommendations to the physician on anticoagulant choice and dosing, depending on patient preference, interacting drugs, and comorbidities. These reports were accessible to the physician to inform the clinical decision-making process. The pharmacist also checked that all relevant diagnostic tests were completed and available for the physician as per guideline recommendations.^{7,10,14} This 'care-set' included blood tests such as urine and electrolyte biochemistry, thyroid function, liver function, full blood examination, lipids, and glycated haemoglobin. The pharmacist would then order any tests required and provide necessary test preparation information to the patient. Imaging tests were also reviewed by the pharmacist and when required, transthoracic echocardiograms and Holter monitors were ordered. A full medication history with corroboration from at least 2 sources was undertaken, as well as symptom review and documentation of European Heart Rhythm Association (EHRA) symptom class scoring.^{14,16} Finally, a formal report was submitted into the hospital's health information system and a copy sent to the patient's primary care doctor and primary pharmacy where indicated. If at any point throughout the consultation urgent medical treatment or assessment was required, the pharmacist escalated the issue to the physician.

Following the pharmacist consultation, the patient would present to the RAAF clinic for a repeat electrocardiogram (ECG) prior to seeing the physician. Subsequently, patients were then discharged to their general practitioner (GP) for long term management with the opportunity to re-refer if needed in the future. Additionally, patients could be referred on to specialist cardiology clinics when indicated, such as for long term heart failure management or electrophysiologist review.

Fig. 1. Pharmacist-physician model of care description from referral to physician consultation.

2.2. Setting for the RAAF clinic

The Grampians Health network services a population of 250,000 people and covers an area of 48,500 km² in regional western Victoria, Australia. The RAAF clinic was situated at the major referral centre within the region, Grampians Health Ballarat, a 785-bed hospital. The implementation of the RAAF clinic occurred between April 2022 and November 2023.

3. Referrals to RAAF

All patients within Grampians Health catchment could be referred to the RAAF clinic for either new diagnosis work-up of AF or for breakthrough symptoms/complications of AF. Referrals could be made from primary care settings by their GP or via the emergency department or acute wards of hospitals. General cardiology referrals for new or exacerbated AF were also redirected to the RAAF service during referral triage.

3.1. Data source and collection

As part of routine clinical care, a dataset of all patients referred to the RAAF service was maintained, with patient referral and attendance data, risk assessments, tests performed, and medication use as per patient self-reporting, as well as a review of dispensing records from their primary pharmacy. Information was extracted from the pharmacist and physician consult letters using a data collection tool and data dictionary to define all variables. All outcome measures were determined prior to the implementation of the RAAF clinic. At 30 days following discharge from clinic, follow up calls were performed by a non-clinician member of the clinic bookings team. During this follow up, patient quality of life and patient experience of the clinic were assessed, with responses entered into the dataset.

3.2. Evaluation method

Due the complex nature of this intervention – being implemented directly into an existing health service, as opposed to a separate trial – a retrospective mixed methods approach was adopted in order to evaluate how the service performed.^{17,18} This involved understanding how the clinic improved access to care compared to current practice; whether guideline recommended assessments were completed; how well evidence-based anticoagulation was prescribed; how anti-arrhythmic medications were prescribed; how quality of life changed throughout the patient's time in the clinic; and whether patients were accepting of the service. The synthesis of service statistics, clinical management, and how patients accepted and engaged with the service, provide an integrated method of evaluation.^{17,19}

4. Outcomes

4.1. Access

Access was assessed by reviewing the proportion of patients who were referred to clinic and who attended at least one appointment, as well as the number of days to first consultation with the pharmacist and physician following clinic referral. We also evaluated the number of appointments attended for the pharmacist and physician components of the clinic, and discharge destination following RAAF clinic attendance. For comparison, the same process was undertaken for general cardiology clinic appointments, where patients would normally have been referred prior to the RAAF service being implemented.

4.1.1. Assessment

Assessment was evaluated by the number of patients receiving risk assessment via CHADSVA score, HASBLED score, and completion of care-set tests, in line with clinical guidelines for AF management and care delivery.^{7,10,12} Treatment with anticoagulation and anti-arrhythmic drugs at baseline and following RAAF clinic attendance were evaluated, including whether changes were made to therapy and whether anticoagulation was appropriately prescribed. The presence of risk assessment completion and appropriate care-set tests sourced were used a marker of appropriate guideline directed implementation of best practice.

4.2. Patient experience

Quality of life was assessed via Health-Related Quality of Life (EQ-5D-5L) at baseline and during the follow up call, and was evaluated using the difference in utility scores from an Australian value set.²⁰ Patient acceptance was evaluated at the follow up call by asking the question “on a scale of 1–10, how likely would you recommend this service to someone with AF?”. The patient was also given the opportunity to provide open-ended responses to explain the reasoning behind their score if they wished. Scores and open-ended responses were transcribed by the non-clinician staff member who made the call.

4.3. Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to describe characteristics of patients attending the service, time to consultation, and proportion of patients receiving changes to the management of their AF following clinic attendance. Mean difference and 95 % confidence intervals were determined for quality of life utility changes from utility scores, and net promoter scores calculated were evaluated using descriptive statistics and previously published methods.^{21,22} All data cleaning, checking, and analyses were conducted in Stata version 18, with the protocol available at <https://github.com/cardiopharmerd/raafeval>.

Open ended responses for patient acceptance were analysed using conventional content analysis.²³ Review of the responses were conducted in duplicate by two independent reviewers (ACL and AL) and then codes were compared and iteratively refined through discussion, defining overarching categories and concepts that captured participants experience of interacting with the RAAF clinic.

4.4. Ethics

Ethics approval and waiver of consent to conduct the retrospective evaluation was obtained from the Grampians Health Ballarat Human Research Ethics Committee (Project number 107482 LNR//BHSSJOG) and Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (43967).

5. Results

5.1. Cohort

Over the course of the implementation of the RAAF clinic service (April 2022 to November 2023), there were 312 patients referred, of which 274 attended at least one appointment with either the pharmacist or physician (Fig. 2). The majority of patients who did not attend the service did not respond to calls to arrange an appointment (7.3 % (23/312)). Of the 274 patients who attended at least one appointment, 97 % (268/274) attended at least one pharmacist appointment, and 91 % (248/274) attended at least one physician appointment. Did-not-attend rates were lower with pharmacist appointments (2.2 % (6/274)) than

Fig. 2. Flow diagram of patient referral and attendance to Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic.

compared with physician appointments (11 % (55/476)). Overall, the median number of appointments attended per patient was 2, made up of 1 pharmacist appointment and 1–2 physician appointments.

The majority of patients seen in the RAAF clinic were aged 60–69 (33 % (90/274)) and 70–79 (35 % (97/274)), with referral sources mainly coming from inpatient wards or the emergency department within the health service, at 36 % (99/274) and 34 % (94/274) respectively (Table 1).

5.2. Access

The median time from hospital discharge (or GP referral date) to first appointment was 23 days (inter-quartile range (IQR) 18–32) (Table 2). When using date of referral received, this reduced to 14 days.^{9–20} The median time between pharmacist and physician appointments (when a pharmacist was initially consulted and subsequently saw a physician), was 28 (14–40) days. In contrast, the median wait-time for general cardiology appointments during this same period was 224 (IQR 47–284) days. Management plans were created for 96 % (263/274) of patients

who attended the service, with 88 % (242/274) having a documented plan for rate or rhythm control. The majority of patients (77 % (212/274)) were discharged to their regular primary care GP, with the remaining patients referred to local specialist services (18 % (48/274)), or to metropolitan based specialist services (5.1 % (14/274)) (Table 2).

5.3. Assessment

Care-set completion was achieved in all patients (274/274), with echocardiograms completed in 79 % (216/274) of patients (Table 1). CHADSVA assessment was documented in 99 % (270/274) of patients, with median CHADSVA of 2 (IQR: 1–3), and 99 % (270/274) of patients having a HASBLED assessment completed.

5.4. Treatment

Treatment for AF was separated into anticoagulation and anti-arrhythmic management. For patients with a low risk of stroke (CHADSVA = 0), 41 % (13/32) were using anticoagulants prior to RAAF

Table 1
Patient characteristics, referral characteristics, and risk assessment completion for the Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic^a.

Total patients	274
Sex	
Female	131 (47.8 %)
Age ranges	
Under 50	16 (5.8 %)
50–59	38 (13.9 %)
60–69	90 (32.8 %)
70–79	97 (35.4 %)
80–89	32 (11.7 %)
90 and above	1 (0.4 %)
Referral source	
Inpatient ward	99 (36.1 %)
Emergency department	94 (34.3 %)
General Practitioner	70 (25.5 %)
External hospital	11 (4.0 %)
Risk assessments	
Care-set completed	274 (100.0 %)
Echocardiogram completed	216 (78.8 %)
CHADSVA Assessment completed	270 (98.5 %)
CHADSVA = 0	32 (11.7 %)
CHADSVA = 1	51 (18.6 %)
CHADSVA = 2	57 (20.8 %)
CHADSVA = 3	71 (25.9 %)
CHADSVA = 4	30 (10.9 %)
CHADSVA = 5	21 (7.7 %)
CHADSVA = 6	8 (2.9 %)
CHADSVA = 7	2 (0.7 %)
CHADSVA = 8	2 (0.7 %)
Median CHADSVA score (IQR)	2 (1–3)
HASBLED assessment completed	270 (98.5 %)

^a Measures presented as total number and percentage (n (%)) or median (IQR).

Table 2
Attendance and discharge statistics for the Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic^a.

Total patients	274
Attendance statistics	
Median time from discharge to first appointment (IQR)	23 (18–32)
Median time from referral to first appointment (IQR)	14 (9–20)
Median time between pharmacist and physician appointment ^b (IQR)	28 (14–40)
Median number of appointments per patient (IQR)	2 (1–3)
Discharge documentation	
Management plan present on discharge from clinic	263 (96.0 %)
Rate or rhythm plan documented on discharge from clinic	242 (88.3 %)
Rhythm control	124 (45.3 %)
Rate control	118 (43.1 %)
No rate/rhythm control plan documented	32 (11.7 %)
Discharge destination from RAAF clinic	
General practitioner	212 (77.4 %)
Public regional cardiology clinic	21 (7.7 %)
Private cardiologist clinic	17 (6.2 %)
Public electrophysiology clinic	12 (4.4 %)
Public regional heart failure clinic	10 (3.6 %)
Metropolitan cardiologist clinic	2 (0.7 %)
Representation outcomes at 30 days post discharge	
Unplanned presentation to emergency department	25 (9.1 %)
Unplanned admission to hospital	19 (6.9 %)

^a Measures presented as total number and percentage (n (%)) unless otherwise stated.

^b Only includes patients who attended both pharmacist and physician appointments.

clinic compared to 19 % (6/32) post clinic (Fig. 3). For CHADSVA = 1, anticoagulant use prior to RAAF clinic was 73 % (37/51) and 75 % (38/51) post clinic. For CHADSVA >1 anticoagulant use was 88 % (168/192)

prior to RAAF clinic and 97 % (186/192) post clinic (Fig. 3 and Supplementary Table 1). When anticoagulants were prescribed by RAAF clinicians, apixaban was used exclusively (no patients were commenced on rivaroxaban, dabigatran, or warfarin).

The use of rate and/or rhythm controlling medications was present in 76 % (208/274) of patients prior to RAAF clinic attendance and in 73 % (201/274) of patients following RAAF clinic attendance (Table 3). The most commonly used medications were beta blockers, with 69 % (188/274) and 67.2 % (184/274) used pre and post RAAF clinic respectively. The second most prescribed medication was digoxin with 10 % (27/274) prior to RAAF clinic and 10 % (28/274) post RAAF clinic. Changes in anti-arrhythmic medication occurred in 35 % (97/274) of patients (Supplement Table 2). The most significant change seen following RAAF clinic attendance was switching to rhythm control with sotalol, with 14 % of patients (37/274) changing to this drug, mostly following cessation of another beta blocker (9 % (24/274)) (Supplement Table 2). Only 8.0 % of patients (22/274) were referred for direct current reversion (DCR).

5.5. Quality of life

There were 57 % (156/274) of patients that completed the baseline and follow up calls where quality of life and net promoter score information was collected. Utility scores showed improvement of quality of life in 53 % (82/156) of patients following participation in the RAAF clinic, with 33 % (52/156) noting a reduction in quality of life and 14 % (22/156) with no change (Table 4). Mean utility scores increased from baseline (0.85 (0.81–0.88)) to follow up (0.88 (0.85–0.91)), with a mean difference of 0.03 (0.00–0.06).

5.6. Patient experience

From the 156 patients that completed follow-up, the mean score for recommending the service to someone with AF was 9.1 (8.8–9.3) (Table 5). This results in a net promoter score of 69 %.²²

Open-ended responses were provided by 56 % (153/274) of all patients, which underwent qualitative conventional content analysis. Feedback was classified into three overarching categories; i) clinic considerations, ii) clinician considerations, and iii) patient experience. Feedback was overwhelmingly positive, as reflected in the mean score for recommending the service. The first category related to the operation of the clinic, including the sub-categories of *workflow*, with participants commenting on the efficiency of service and use of technology; *Organisational culture*, which captured patients perspectives on how accommodating and accessible the service was, along with *teamwork*, portraying the perceived synergy between the clinic pharmacist, physician, and wider health service. *Clinician considerations* reflected participants perceptions of the clinic staff, identifying that *patient centredness*, and *clinical knowledge* were central contributors to positive patient-clinician interactions. It was determined that the combined contributions of the clinic and clinicians, impacted (both positively and negatively) how health care was communicated to patients effectively, and subsequently, their overall experience. *Patient experience* was trichotomized into; what patients know (i.e. enhanced knowledge and understanding), how they feel (both in terms of their health and a sense of being valued as an individual), and their continuity of care (ease of follow up and ongoing self-management). The interconnected categories and subcategories are represented visually in Fig. 4, with exemplary participant quotes presented in Supplement Table 3.

Fig. 3. Anticoagulant use pre and post Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic attendance grouped by CHADSVA score ranges.

Table 3

Anti-arrhythmic medication use pre and post Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic attendance.

	Pre-RAAF	Post-RAAF
Total	274	274
Any anti-arrhythmic medication	208 (75.9 %)	201 (73.4 %)
Beta blocker	188 (68.6 %)	184 (67.2 %)
Metoprolol	133 (48.5 %)	93 (33.9 %)
Sotalol	32 (11.7 %)	63 (23.0 %)
Bisoprolol	9 (3.3 %)	15 (5.5 %)
Atenolol	11 (4.0 %)	10 (3.6 %)
Nebivolol	2 (0.7 %)	3 (1.1 %)
Calcium channel blocker	8 (2.9 %)	7 (2.6 %)
Diltiazem	6 (2.2 %)	7 (2.6 %)
Verapamil	2 (0.7 %)	0
Flecainide	7 (2.6 %)	9 (3.3 %)
Amiodarone	16 (5.8 %)	13 (4.7 %)
Digoxin	27 (9.9 %)	28 (10.2 %)

Table 4

Health related quality of life (HR-QoL) utility scores at baseline and 30 days following discharge from clinic^a.

Total RAAF patients	274
Completed HR-QoL follow up	156/274 (56.9 %)
Mean EQ-5D Utility score (95 % confidence interval)	
At baseline	0.85 (0.81–0.88)
30 days following RAAF discharge	0.88 (0.85–0.91)
Mean difference	0.03 (0.00–0.06)
Change in EQ-5D Utility score	
Improvement	82 (52.6 %)
Reduction	52 (33.3 %)
No change	22 (14.1 %)

^a Measures presented as total number and percentage (n (%)) unless otherwise stated.

6. Discussion

Using a mixed methods approach, our findings demonstrate the successful implementation of a rapid access pharmacist-physician model of care focussed on the assessment and management of AF, as demonstrated with reduced wait times, improved guideline concordant care, and high levels of patient satisfaction.^{19,24}

Table 5

Patient net promoter score summary and feedback completion for Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic^a.

Total RAAF patients	274
Completed NPS follow up	156/274 (56.9 %)
Detractors (scored 1–6)	1 (0.64 %)
	2 (0.72 %)
	3 (1.82 %)
	4 (2.56 %)
	5 (3.18 %)
	6 (3.85 %)
Neutral (scored 7–8)	4 (2.56 %)
	7 (4.48 %)
	8 (5.06 %)
Promoter (scored 9–10)	24 (15.38 %)
	9 (5.73 %)
	10 (6.20 %)
Mean NPS score (95 % confidence interval)	92 (58.97 %)
	9.06 (8.81–9.30)
NPS Score^b	69.2 %
Written feedback for qualitative analysis	153/274 (55.8 %)

^a Measures presented as total number and percentage (n (%)), unless otherwise stated.

^b Equation for Net Promoter Score = (Promoters – Detractors)/Completed NPS.²²

6.1. Clinic service

A key motivation behind the implementation of a rapid access model of care is to minimise the time window between identification of an issue (the referral), and the issue being addressed (the consultation).⁶ Compared to our health network’s existing cardiology services, we saw a reduction in time between referral and consultation from 224 days with general cardiology to 14 days with the RAAF. A cardiologist-led RAAF model developed in Canada reduced the time to first consultation with a cardiologist from 111 days to 63 days.¹² This was also demonstrated in an Australian cardiologist led arrhythmia service, showing a reduction from over 90 days–10.5 days.⁶ Therefore, the results of our pharmacist-physician model are comparable to cardiologist led models in terms of providing accelerated care. However, it is imperative that any new model of care not only considers the quantity and efficiency of care, but also to consider the patient experience.²⁴ Our model’s addition of a pharmacist consult prior to the physician consult has been previously shown to enhance patient experience in outpatient cardiology, namely around improving the confidence and knowledge of patients attending the service.^{11,25,26} We saw similar patterns in both the quantitative results of service acceptance with mean score of 9.1, but also the qualitative conventional content analysis. For example, one patient

Fig. 4. Conceptual model surrounding patient experience with the Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic via conventional content analysis of follow-up survey data.

commented that “Everything was explained well and clearly. Was a very pleasant experience and very efficient (Supplement Table 3, patient 28)”. This demonstrates that the model of care was not only efficient, but was accepted and valued by the patients.

A challenge facing all outpatient cardiology services is the ability to provide services that are accessible, without creating further burden, or shifting care from primary practice to ‘specialist only’ services.²⁷ In order to provide a service that can continue to offer rapid access, patients need to enter the service, and then be discharged as soon as practicable to maintain patient flow.²⁸ Our service allowed for most patients (77.4 %) to be discharged to their GP with a management plan within 3 appointments. Furthermore, one of those appointments was the first pharmacist consult, further reducing the burden on the physician and allowing increased patient throughput. We saw that despite only having a small number of consults to build rapport and a management plan, patients described the service as efficient and thorough.

6.2. Clinical assessment and treatment

Delivery of rapid care should not be at expense of the quality of care that is provided.²⁸ For AF, guidelines stipulate the assessment of stroke risk and collection of biochemical and imaging tests, which are necessary to ensure treatment plans are patient-specific.^{4,10,26} Multiple trials have demonstrated that when pharmacists are engaged in risk factor assessment, significant improvements are seen in screening and risk reduction.^{26,29} This was echoed in our findings with all patients receiving a completed care-set and 96 % of patients receiving management plans on discharge. These are known quality indicators for ensuring the best possible care for adults with AF.³⁰ Additionally, the review of antiarrhythmic therapy and subsequent change of therapy in 35.4 % of patients presenting to RAAF clinic indicates potentially inappropriate antiarrhythmic therapy at time of referral. Nonetheless, the continued review of antiarrhythmic medications is also listed by the

European Heart Rhythm Association and Heart Rhythm Society as a quality indicator for ensuring good clinical outcomes.³⁰

Our anticoagulant use data show similar increases in baseline use over time from 30 to 40 % of people with CHADSVA >1 from a 2011–2013 Victorian cohort to 88 % at baseline for our cohort.⁹ This aligns with global increases in anticoagulant use observed since the introduction of NOACs in AF with 42 % prevalence in 2010 compared to 78 % in 2018.³¹ Our service did still improve on baseline use of anticoagulation with an increase in the use of anticoagulation in those at higher risk of stroke with CHADSVA >1 from 88 % to 97.4 %. Additionally, our RAAF clinic rationalised therapy well across all patients, with deprescribing of potentially unnecessary anticoagulation with CHADSVA of 0 from 40.6 % to 18.8 %.

Having a collaborative model with an intentional focus on teamwork also means that the benefits seen in pharmacist and physician/cardiologist models are combined, compared to other models where clinicians may work in isolation of one another.¹² This was evident in feedback received from patients during follow up, with patients noting coordination between their tests, their pharmacist telehealth appointments, and their physician appointments; creating a sense of being cared for (Supplement Table 3 – teamwork and patient experience). When compared with the Safer Care Victoria partnering with healthcare framework principles of: personalised care; shared decision making; equity and inclusion; working together; and effective communication, we saw many similarities.³² The positive feedback surrounding patient centredness, inclusion of the patient and GP in decision making and follow up, as well as positive comments surrounding respect and empathy, align closely with frameworks aim of consistent patient-centred care.³²

The RAAF clinic introduced additional appointments in close succession, as well as a high likelihood of further investigations and changes to medications. Despite this additional burden of treatment, there were no negative comments made by patients regarding this. In fact, many

patients expressed that increased knowledge and thorough service led to relief and the ability to feel “very comfortable with the diagnosis now” (Supplement Table 3 – patient 63). This suggests that targeted therapy delivered rapidly in a patient-centred model, while increasing burden of treatment on the patient, is actually preferred to prolonged treatment windows and less time spent with clinicians.²⁴

7. Limitations

We conducted a retrospective mixed method evaluation of an implementation project rather than a randomized controlled trial, which

Supplemental Table 1

Anticoagulant use pre and post Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic attendance

CHADSVA score	Total	Pre-Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic attendance						Pre-Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic attendance					
		Any	Apixaban	Rivaroxaban	Dabigatran	Warfarin	None	Anticoagulated	Apixaban	Rivaroxaban	Dabigatran	Warfarin	None
CHADSVA = 0	32	13 (40.6 %)	13 (40.6 %)	0 (0.0 %)	0 (0.0 %)	0 (0.0 %)	19 (59.4 %)	6 (18.8 %)	6 (18.8 %)	0 (0.0 %)	0 (0.0 %)	0 (0.0 %)	26 (81.2 %)
CHADSVA = 1	51	37 (72.5 %)	30 (58.8 %)	1 (2.0 %)	5 (9.8 %)	1 (2.0 %)	14 (27.5 %)	38 (74.5 %)	31 (60.8 %)	1 (2.0 %)	5 (9.8 %)	1 (2.0 %)	13 (25.5 %)
CHADSVA > 1	192	168 (88.0 %)	136 (71.2 %)	6 (3.1 %)	23 (12.0 %)	3 (1.6 %)	23 (12.0 %)	186 (97.4 %)	149 (78.0 %)	4 (2.1 %)	30 (15.7 %)	3 (1.6 %)	5 (2.6 %)

means comparisons are made to quality indicators rather than a control group. Additionally, limits on the size of the sample and follow up windows do not permit the ability to understand if there are meaningful differences in stroke and hospitalization rates between those who received and did not receive the RAAF clinic service. Matched cohort studies have been done to account for this with other arrhythmia clinic services,⁶ but given the temporal trends in anticoagulant use and the window where the COVID-19 pandemic was associated with changes to patient presentation and outpatient services, this would be unlikely to provide clarity, but instead introduce more sources of bias.³¹

Patient acceptance of the service was primarily defined using net promoter scores, which have been identified as a potentially unreliable measure in healthcare when there is often no other choice for service.²² However, given there was a choice to not engage with the pharmacist arm of the service, this measure may be suitable given 97 % (268/274) chose to engage with the pharmacist consultation prior to seeing the physician. Furthermore, our investigation through qualitative analysis of feedback assisted in providing more detail around the score.

8. Conclusions

In a healthcare landscape with limited resources and an increasing burden of chronic diseases such as atrial fibrillation, models of care that utilise existing skillsets can enhance and accelerate access to healthcare are imperative. The RAAF service demonstrated accelerated access to healthcare that improved risk assessment, evidence-based medication management, and was highly accepted and valued by the patients receiving the service.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adam C. Livori: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Rasanth Kuruppumullage:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Mardi Simmons:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Data curation. **Aili Langford:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Zanfina Ademi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **J. Simon Bell:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Renee Dimond:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Jedidiah I.**

Morton: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Data statement

The individual-level data underlying this article cannot be shared publicly due to privacy reasons. However, the protocol containing all code used to generate this study, along with aggregate statistics on the dataset are available [here](#).

a) Measures presented as total number and percentage (n (%))

Supplement Table 2

Changes made to anti-arrhythmic medication pre and post Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation (RAAF) clinic attendance

	Total	274
Any change to anti-arrhythmic medication		97 (35.4 %)
Beta blockers	Added	11 (4.0 %)
	Ceased	24 (8.8 %)
	Changed (excluding sotalol)	5 (1.8 %)
	Switched to sotalol	37 (13.5 %)
Calcium channel blockers	Added	1 (0.4 %)
	Ceased	2 (0.7 %)
	Drug change	6 (2.2 %)
Flecainide	Added	2 (0.7 %)
Amiodarone	Added	1 (0.4 %)
	Ceased	4 (1.5 %)
Digoxin	Added	11 (4.0 %)
	Ceased	10 (3.6 %)
Procedure	DCR referral	22 (8.0 %)

Supplement Table 3

Content analysis quotes and associated net promoter scores associated with clinic and clinician considerations, communication, and patient experience.

Model of care component	Quotes from corresponding patients ^a (net promoter score)
Clinic considerations:	9:
Workflow – Efficiency	Very efficient, staff were very good and on time (10/10)
	28:
	Everything was explained well and clearly. Was a very pleasant experience and very efficient. (10/10)
	52:
	Got to see the doctor very quickly and happy with the tests performed at the time and the results which were also given to her very quickly (10/10)
	90:
	The service was great, everything was very efficient, and I didn't have to wait around. (10/10)
	98:
	Felt well looked after, efficient service, felt

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Supplement Table 3 (continued)

Model of care component	Quotes from corresponding patients ^a (net promoter score)
	everyone was doing their best (9/10)
	110: In straight away to be seen, professional, no waiting at appointment. Showed duty of care. (9/10)
	127: Everything was good, everyone was on time (8/10)
Clinic considerations:	48: Was happy with the service. Was grateful to receive text messages when clinic couldn't get hold of him (10/10)
Workflow – Technology	76: Minor hiccup with the receptionist telling her misinformation about her needing to come in for a procedure which was not the case. (10/10)
	149: Doctor's computer wasn't working so he could not review her results and there was no follow up after this so she was never informed of her results (5/10)
Clinic considerations:	16: [I] was given notice of appointments with ample time to plan as I come from out of town (10/10)
Organisational culture – Accommodating	17: Found everybody extremely helpful and couldn't speak more highly of this service overall. Quick, informative and friendly and would recommend anybody without hesitation (10/10)
Clinic considerations:	54: Happy with service. Great no cost public service (10/10)
Organisational culture – Accessibility	106: It was a simple and easy process (9/10)
	123: Overall everyone was friendly and process was easy to go through (8/10)
	150: Is yet to attend cardiologist appointment, has had 2 appointment rebooked. Has been unhappy with follow ups and communication as he has constantly had to prompt his GP to chase things up and chase up appointments (5/10)
Clinic considerations:	56: [The pharmacist] was great at making contact and set up echo which hadn't been by ED so everything flowed and he made sure everything went beautifully (10/10)
Organisational culture – Teamwork	59: Everyone was very accommodating and flexible when patient had conflicting appointment times (10/10)
	88: The doctor was amazing, knew everything about me as the patient and was exceptionally well prepared, changed a medication that has made a huge difference. Overall a fabulous experience. (10/10)
Clinician considerations:	13: Thought it was really good, the [doctor and pharmacist] were really helpful and explained the condition well. (10/10)
Patient centredness – Respect	37: Felt like everyone cared and was interested in [patient's] health. (10/10)
	58: Extremely happy with the clinic experience felt very valued by the Pharmacist and the Doctor. (10/10)
	80: Wonderful people and felt she was treated with respect. Any question she asked was answered. Extremely happy with overall experience. (10/10)
	83: I really loved the pharmacy consult with [the pharmacist] straight away, he spent heaps of time explaining things. Loved [the doctor] as well and

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Supplement Table 3 (continued)

Model of care component	Quotes from corresponding patients ^a (net promoter score)
	he didn't make me feel rushed. As it was a new diagnosis it was potentially scary but felt very comfortable. [Pharmacy technician] was good with the initial phone call explaining the process. (10/10)
	97: I found it all very approachable and helpful, was given all the time I needed. (9/10)
Clinician considerations:	15: They were very patient and kind at the clinic (10/10)
Patient centredness – Empathy	85: The pharmacist was absolutely fantastic and couldn't have been more helpful. Doctor was great and prescribed a new tablet on the day and [The pharmacist] walked me down to the Pharmacy to make sure everything was OK. (10/10)
	114: All staff quite pleasant and very helpful. Husband attended clinic with her and also thought they were treated well (9/10)
Clinician considerations:	11: Very professional, friendly, no waiting for around hours. (10/10)
Patient centredness – Professional	127: Everything was good, everyone was on time. (8/10)
	138: Efficient and timely manner and cardiologist was honest with patient which he appreciated. (8/10)
Clinician considerations:	20: The doctor was right on the money, very thorough and took the time to explain everything at my level which I found very helpful and made it easy to feel like I knew exactly what was going on. (10/10)
Patient centredness – Thorough	27: Would highly recommend the pharmacy component of the clinic. [The pharmacist] was amazing and very thorough. He went through all my medications with me and helped me with my side effects. He was a great listener and followed things up for me. (10/10)
	41: The pharmacist was great and very thorough. The cardiologist was also very good. (10/10)
	44: Very thorough, hospital care he had could not be faulted, aftercare has been brilliant, totally satisfied. (10/10)
	57: All concerns addressed very thoroughly and is very happy with the follow up received. Can't fault anything about the service. (10/10)
Patient experience:	50: Great service and the understanding [from clinician], everything explained very well.
What they know – Understanding	119: Happy with the knowledge of the team and that all treatment options were explained and discussed. (8/10)
	156: Only a phone appointment. Felt the doctor was 'useless', kept repeating himself and was contradictory. Patient and wife felt very confused. (1/10)
Patient experience:	1: Clarified concerns and is now on appropriate meds and symptoms have been relieved by this and it happened straight away. (10/10)
How they feel – Relief	22: I was put at ease and helped out really quickly and efficiently. Pharmacist was very helpful and went above and beyond. (10/10)
	46: Happy with the service and the doctor and was a

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Supplement Table 3 (continued)

Model of care component	Quotes from corresponding patients ^a (net promoter score)
	relief to have all the tests to have answers. (10/10)
	60: [Pharmacist and doctor] have done a fantastic job, my heart has been working very well. (10/10)
	61: Explained everything very well, test results etc and was able to understand and feel comfortable as a result. (10/10)
	63: Explained everything in simple terms so all information was understood and patient feels very comfortable with diagnosis now. (10/10)
	84: Everybody went out of their way to make me feel at ease and were very helpful. (10/10)
Patient experience: How they feel – Care	45: Extremely happy with the service. Felt very well looked after. Thought the clinic was well organized. (10/10)
	82: Felt like people wanted to help and listened. (10/10)
	107: Dr was very nice, felt she received very good advice. Pharmacist was also great and very helpful. (9/10)
	108: If you have never had this condition and need to get information this clinic was fabulous. I was given all the information and everything was explained to me really well. (9/10)
Patient experience: Continuity of care– Self-management	40: It's an absolutely fantastic service and follow up was good. Doctor was great and phone service as well. Change of medication has me feeling well currently. Have already suggested to a work colleague that they should get referred to this clinic. (10/10)
	86: Was very happy with the service. Everything was very thorough and I haven't been having any problems with my tablets or management (10/10)
	87: Good for my health. Back to full time work now. (10/10)
	96: Tweaked my tablets which made a difference, very happy with the overall experience. (9/10)
Patient experience: Continuity of care– Follow up	53: GP [has] now has ordered some follow up tests he would not have done otherwise. (10/10)
	66: Very happy with the service and that they communicated with my GP. (10/10)
	94: Everything was explained clearly from start to finish and information was forwarded to my GP (9/10)
	95: Clinic was fine but [patient] wasn't sure how long to keep taking blood thinner tablets. Followed up with her GP (9/10)
	119: Has been extremely grateful for the services of the hospital and was happy with the service of the clinic. Was just a bit disappointed that there was no further follow up, especially given the cardiologist knew how anxious he was about being on blood thinners (8/10)
Linking component: Communication	32: I thought it was very well organized. Was phoned the next day by the doctor to follow up as they had more to add from the day before and wanted to stop a medication straight away so I thought that was great service (10/10)

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Supplement Table 3 (continued)

Model of care component	Quotes from corresponding patients ^a (net promoter score)
	141: Felt he could have been informed more than he was. GP had to fill in a lot of blanks. But felt the clinic was well organized and efficient (7/10)
	142: Felt the doctor was very good and the staff were very supportive and helpful and made her feel very relaxed. However, received a confusing phone-call post appointment due to lack of communication between departments. (7/10)
	155: Seems to take a while to get things done, service is very good, he thought that rapid response would be the first week, but it's taken almost 2 months (DCR is booked in for today) - which is a bit disappointing. (3/10)

a) Items within square brackets used for removal of clinician or patient names given during feedback.

Funding

The authors acknowledge funding provided by Safer Care Victoria as part of the Rapid Access Atrial Fibrillation Clinic initiative. Safer Care Victoria approved the model of care and provided necessary funds to conduct the service over the implementation period. Ongoing funding for the service has been provided by Grampians Health via state and national activity-based funding schemes.

Declaration of interest

AL Consulting for Sanofi, Boehringer Ingelheim, Novartis.

RK, MS, AL, ZA, JIM, RD No conflicts to declare relevant to this publication.

JSB is supported by a National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) Boosting Dementia Research Leadership Fellowship and has received grant funding or consulting funds from the NHMRC, Medical Research Future Fund, Victorian Government Department of Health, Dementia Australia Research Foundation, Yulgilbar Foundation, Aged Care Quality and Safety Commission, Dementia Centre for Research Collaboration, Pharmaceutical Society of Australia, Society of Hospital Pharmacists of Australia, GlaxoSmithKline Supported Studies Programme, Amgen, and several aged care provider organizations unrelated to this work. All grants and consulting funds were paid to the employing institution.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the project management support provided by Safer Care Victoria and the Cardiovascular Learning Health Network. The authors also acknowledge the Internal Medical Services and Pharmacy departments of Grampians Health for approving the implementation and subsequent ongoing funding for this model of care.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2025.03.005>.

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